

**EMPOWERING FINANCIAL INCLUSION: GOVERNMENT SCHEMES AND
FINTECH INNOVATIONS”**

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ABSTRACT

Mobile banking has evolved as a potent instrument for facilitating financial transactions and managing personal finances. Financial inclusion, particularly in developing nations have a high level of mobile phone adoption, is a significant area of concern. The utilization of mobile banking enables individuals to conveniently access financial services via their mobile devices. Mobile phones are of particular significance for individuals residing in geographically isolated regions with limited access to resources and possess the ability to utilize physical bank branches. Mobile banking also facilitates individuals to facilitate expeditious and convenient transactions, obviating the need for extensive travel. The research emphasizes on the technological facets of banking on the widespread recognition of the pivotal role that technology and financial technology (Fintech), which play in advancing financial inclusion. The utilization of a structured questionnaire additionally allows the researcher to facilitate a comparative analysis of the respondents' answers. Various participants can be utilized to uncover patterns and trends within the low-income population. The present study focuses on the attitudes and preferences of various demographic

groups with regard to the adoption as well as practice of mobile banking facilities. The researcher's primary area of interest lies in the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana Scheme. The significance of scheme and mobile banking lies in their ability to underscore the importance of these technologies and fostering financial inclusiveness. It additionally emphasizes the crucial significance that the realms of financial services in developing countries are in the process of advancing economically, socially, and technologically.

Keywords: Fintech, Financial inclusion, Mobile banking, Pension, Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana

Introduction

Financial inclusion is becoming an essential component of sustainable development. It strives to give access to formal financial services and products for underprivileged and underrepresented communities [1]. Financial inclusion is assessed based on the presence of bank accounts, savings, bank loans and utilization of financial facilities. Financial inclusion, as defined by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), refers to the ongoing efforts to offer access to diverse variety of monetary products and services using new methods, such as financial education. Financial inclusion is acknowledged as a method to empower marginalized folks, enabling them to priorities schooling, enterprise, and proficiently handle financial uncertainties [2]. In India, the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) recognizes the significance of financial inclusion and has implemented various measures to enhance financial inclusion efforts under the National Policy for Financial Inclusion 2019-2024. One of the processes involves assigning a strategic role to micro-financial institutes, self-help groups and banking facilities, alongside official commercial finance systems [3]. Financial inclusion is a fundamental priority in the political and economic agendas of emerging countries. It facilitates inclusive growth by enabling individuals, especially those who are marginalized and impoverished, to avail themselves of official financial services [4]

Through research, it was discovered that in India by 2014, there were over 900 million mobile phones however merely 250 million linked bank accounts only. This highlighted the significant potential for utilizing technology to expand banking services and achieve social benefits [5]. This is where the role of Fintech comes into play, as it enables cost-effective branch expansion. The banks were also involved in offering technologically enabled services to meet the needs of customers. In August 2014, the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY) was announced by Government of India under the National Mission for Financial Inclusion [6, 7]. This initiative aims to provide various financial facilities to marginalized sectors of people. It seeks to achieve universal access to banking facilities, enhance financial knowledge, besides enable access to insurance, credit as well as pension services. The PMJDY aims to provide excepted sections, such as weaker sections and low-income groups, with access to a range of financial services. These services include basic savings bank accounts, insurance, need-based credit, pensions and remittance facilities. Achieving significant penetration at a reasonable price can only be accomplished through the efficient utilization of technology [8]. PMJDY is a national enterprise

intended at attaining complete financial inclusion for every household in the country through an integrated strategy. The strategy aims to provide universal access to banking facilities, justifying that every household has minimum one banking account. It also includes initiatives to encourage financial knowledge in addition to facilitate access to insurance, credit and pension services [9]. Furthermore, the recipients would receive a Repay Debit card that includes integrated accident insurance coverage of ₹ 1 lakh. PMJDY accounts are suitable for Pradhan Mantri Jeevan Jyoti Bima Yojana (PMJJBY), Direct Benefit Transfer (DBT), Atal Pension Yojana (APY), Pradhan Mantri Suraksha Bima Yojana (PMSBY), Micro Units Development and Refinance Agency Bank (MUDRA) scheme [10].

The distinctive transformation of digital infrastructure is a result of the exceptional national innovation known as the India Stack. This innovation encompasses a digital identification and payment system that relies on open application programming interfaces (APIs). By integrating with Aadhaar, the national identity system with 1.3 billion users, it has effectively enhanced financial accessibility for consumers, hence promoting financial inclusion. Dinesh Tyagi, CEO of CSC e-Government Services India, the government operator of e-government service centres in rural and distant areas, stated that Open-stack technology is the fundamental basis of UPI, which has revolutionized digital payments in India [11]. The government is actively endorsing open stack technology to facilitate rapid integration and not only supported the expansion of conventional public sector banks, but also played a role in promoting the development of private Fintech enterprises, thereby expediting the acceptance and utilization of this technology. India's digital revolution offers these services to citizens at no cost, which is a distinctive feature. Simultaneously, policymakers are closely considering another significant investment in the future of digital currencies, which might have far-reaching consequences for the economy [12]. A considerable segment of the population in numerous nations continues to be marginalized from the official financial system, encountering obstacles while attempting to obtain crucial financial facilities like savings accounts, insurance, credit as well as payment methods. Towards addressing this dilemma, governments and Fintech companies have implemented many programmes to augment financial inclusion. The researcher's primary area of interest lies in the PMJDY Scheme. This research study examines the impact of government schemes and Fintech innovations on promoting financial inclusion, providing insights into their possible advantages, difficulties, and collaborations.

Methodology

The study population for assessing the impact of PMJDY financial inclusion research consists of the banked population in India, comprising those who have bank account or formal access to financial services. The study will examine the effects of PMJDY schemes on financial inclusion. Due to constraints in time, effort, and cost, it is not feasible to study all beneficiaries of PMJDY and Mobile Banking in Financial Inclusion. Therefore, a structured questionnaire will be administered to the researcher through a Google survey sheet. The researcher will ask questions

and record the responses in an Excel sheet. The researcher has obtained approximately 400 responses. The duration of the study is from 2018 to 2023. The data from the government's official website is utilized to evaluate the growth of the projects. Data is collected from beneficiaries of Government Schemes and Fintech-Mobile Banking in Financial Inclusion through the use of a standardized questionnaire. The secondary data is obtained from many sources such as RBI, IBEF, World Bank, Global F-index, Department of Financial Service- Ministry of Finance India, Books, periodicals, and Website data. The process of analyzing data involves the utilization of the Chi-Square test and ANOVA.

Results and Discussion

The data shows the responses of respondents towards having a PMJDY account. Of the 400 respondents, 172 (68%) answered "Yes" when asked if they have a PMJDY account. Out of those 172 respondents who said "Yes", it can be assumed that they have a bank account and are therefore included in the formal financial system. This can be seen as a positive indicator of financial inclusion. On the other hand, 85 (32%) respondents answered "No" when asked if they have a PMJDY account. It is clear from the table that these respondents have other types of bank accounts and are included in the formal financial system. Additionally, 133 respondents answered that they do not have a bank account. This indicates a lack of financial inclusion, as these individuals are likely to be excluded from formal financial services and may rely on informal financial services, which may be more expensive and less secure. The PMJDY program aims to increase financial inclusion by providing bank accounts to individuals who do not have them, along with other financial services. Response towards having PMJDY account is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Response towards having PMJDY account

Role of PMJDY in Financial Inclusion

The PMJDY by the Government of India is a financial inclusion platform launched in 2014 with the aim of providing access to financial services to all households in India. The program has played a significant role in promoting financial inclusion in the country by making it easier for people to open bank accounts, access credit, insurance, and pension services, and make digital transactions. PMJDY has contributed to financial inclusion in India such as,

Increased access to banking services: PMJDY has helped to increase the number of people with bank accounts, especially among those who were previously unbanked or under-banked. This has enabled them to access a range of financial services and benefit from the formal financial system.

Encouraged savings and reduced reliance on informal channels: PMJDY has incentivized people to save money by providing them with access to interest-bearing accounts, and this has helped to reduce reliance on informal channels of finance such as moneylenders.

Improved financial literacy: PMJDY has also helped to improve financial literacy among the population by encouraging them to use digital banking services and providing them with information on how to manage their finances effectively.

Enabled access to credit: PMJDY has enabled people to access credit from formal financial institutions, which was previously difficult for many people without a credit history or collateral.

Largely, PMJDY has played a crucial role in fostering financial inclusion in India by making banking services more accessible to all. The program has helped to bring millions of people into the formal financial system, which has helped to boost economic growth and reduce poverty. The study data for PMJDY is taken from the secondary source from the PMJDY website. The following data gives the details on the number of beneficiaries from the year 2014 to 2023 bifurcated in Public sector banks, private sector banks and regional rural banks.

Table 1. PMJDY beneficiaries at rural/semi urban bank

Bank Type	PMJDY: Number of Beneficiaries at rural/semi urban bank branches									
	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Public Sector Banks	45119656	61755432	94292475	123374176	136690134	151884173	164646664	205405169	221260197	237600000
Regional Rural Banks	15717870	21456972	32571067	39797319	42508141	50253598	54676843	66167583	71595364	77200000
Private Sector Banks	1511386	3559953	4843551	5492044	5997883	6858783	6980195	6917873	7038975	6900100
Total	62348912	86772357	131707093	168663539	185196158	208996554	226303702	278490625	299894536	107960100

The PMJDY has achieved tremendous success. The Government of India initiated this programme in 2014 proposing financial facilities towards citizens, with a particular focus on the impoverished segments of society. The most recent data indicates that the programme has successfully facilitated the opening of bank accounts for over 43.04 crore individuals nationwide since its establishment, resulting in a substantial sum of Rs. 146,231 crores.

An outstanding accomplishment of the strategy is its emphasis on promoting financial inclusion. The number of PMJDY accounts has increased by a factor of three, from 2015 to 2021. In addition, 55% of the individuals who have Jan-Dhan accounts are females, besides 67% of these accounts located in semi-urban and rural regions. This demonstrates the efficacy of the initiative in effectively engaging individuals who were previously marginalized from the financial system. The operational status of 86% of PMJDY accounts serves as further evidence of the scheme's success. This indicates that individuals are actively utilizing the accounts for their monetary activities. Furthermore, the cumulative count of RuPay cards distributed to PMJDY account holders has surpassed 31.23 crore, marking yet another noteworthy milestone.

The plan has also been instrumental in providing essential assistance to the underprivileged amidst the Covid-19 outbreak. During the shutdown, a sum of Rs. 30,945 crores has been deposited to the bank accounts of female payees under the Prime Minister Garib Kalyan Yojana. This has alleviated their financial hardship during these arduous circumstances. The efficacy of the plan in providing financial services to the most impoverished individuals is evident from the fact that PMJDY account holders over 51 million accept DBT from the government through several programmes. Overall, the success of the PMJDY is a clear indication of the government's unwavering dedication to promoting financial inclusion and fostering inclusive economic development. The plan has revolutionised the country's financial environment, enabling even the most marginalized individuals in society to avail themselves of financial services.

PMJDY and Bank Account

The PMJDY is a nationwide initiative with the objective of ensuring universal access to financial services, including credit, banking and savings accounts, pension, and insurance, for every household. The PMJDY comprises various essential elements and constituents, such as Zero-Balance Accounts, RuPay Debit Cards, Accidental Insurance Cover, Overdraft Facility, and Mobile Banking. It facilitates financial inclusion through:

Bringing the Unbanked into the Formal System: Before the implementation of the PMJDY, a substantial segment of India's populace lacked accesses to official banking facilities. The objective of PMJDY was to alleviate this problem by offering financial services to even the most remote regions of the country.

Boosting Savings: With the availability of zero-balance accounts, people who were previously excluded from the formal banking system now have the opportunity to save their money in a secure and interest-bearing account. This has encouraged a savings culture among the unbanked.

Direct Benefit Transfer (DBT): The linkage of PMJDY accounts with government schemes has streamlined the process of disbursing subsidies and benefits directly into the accounts of beneficiaries. This has reduced leakages and ensured that the intended recipients receive their entitlements.

Promoting Financial Literacy: The PMJDY has also facilitated the enhancement of financial literacy among the underprivileged population who do not have access to banking services. Bank accounts have fostered greater familiarity with banking operations and financial transactions among individuals, representing a crucial stride towards achieving financial inclusion.

Digital Payments and Transactions: The PMJDY has played a pivotal role in facilitating the adoption of digital payments and transactions, hence stimulating the expansion of Fintech enterprises. Account holders are progressively engaging in digital transactions, both online and at Point of Sale (PoS) terminals, thanks to the availability of RuPay debit cards and mobile banking. This has created new opportunities for Fintech companies to create and advance digital payment systems.

E-KYC (Know Your Customer): To expedite the account opening process, PMJDY introduced e-KYC, which allows for paperless and instantaneous customer verification using Aadhaar biometric data. This innovative approach has reduced the time and cost of customer onboarding and has potential applications in other Fintech services.

Financial Inclusion Apps: Several Fintech companies have developed mobile apps that cater to the needs of PMJDY account holders. These apps provide a user-friendly interface to access account information, make transactions, and even avail of microloans. Such apps have been a boon for people who are not well-versed in traditional banking methods.

Data Analytics and Credit Scoring: The numerous volumes of data produced by PMJDY transactions have proven to be a lucrative opportunity for Fintech companies. Utilizing this data can be advantageous for credit scoring and risk evaluation, simplifying the process of granting credit to previously marginalized communities. Fintech firms are presently employing sophisticated algorithms to evaluate the creditworthiness of individuals by analyzing their transaction history.

Insurtech Innovations: The inclusion of accidental insurance coverage in the PMJDY has led to the emergence of Insurtech companies that provide cost-effective insurance solutions specifically designed for the general population. These organizations utilize technology to develop efficient and cost-efficient insurance solutions.

Considering the hypothesis “There is a significant difference in having a bank account and having a PMJDY”, Chi Square Test is done.

Table 2. Chi Square Test of PMJDY and Bank Account

Particular	Normal Bank Account	PMJDY Account
Chi-Square	37.501 ^a	34.862 ^b
df	1	2
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000

The data shows that out of 400 participants, 187 have a PMJDY account, 160 have a bank account, and 53 have no bank Account. The chi-square test statistic for the association between having a PMJDY account and having a bank account is 34.862. Since the p-value is lower than the significance level of 0.05, authors may conclude that there is a statistically significant difference between having a bank account and having a PMJDY account. Hence, there is a significant difference between having a PMJDY account and having a bank account, and between having a bank account and not having a PMJDY account.

Table 3. Chi Square Test of Financial Inclusion via Mobile Banking

Particular	Mobile Banking via Bank Application	Mobile Banking via Private Application	Mobile Banking via BHIM	Mobile Banking via Payment Bank	Mobile Banking via All Methods
Chi-Square	57.965 ^a	.861 ^a	39.861 ^a	.136 ^a	.136 ^a
df	1	1	1	1	1
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.352	.000	.720	.720

Chi-square test is performed to ascertain the presence of a statistically significant association among different methods of utilizing mobile banking, such as through a bank application, private application, BHIM, Payment Bank, or a combination of all of them. The test statistics table 3 displays the outcomes of the chi-square test, encompassing p-value, degrees of freedom and chi-square value for each mode of mobile banking utilization. The p-values for utilizing mobile banking through Bank Application, BHIM, and all the aforementioned methods are below .05, suggesting a substantial correlation between the manner of mobile banking usage and the frequency of usage for these methods. However, when utilizing mobile banking through Private Application and Payment Bank, the p-values above .05, suggesting that there is no correlation regarding significance statistically between the manner of using mobile banking for these methods.

Table 4. Satisfaction level towards PMJDY via mobile banking

Features	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Easiness	1.466	3	0.489	1.990	0.117
Availability	3.704	3	1.235	2.565	0.058
Control	3.273	3	1.091	2.031	0.114
Secure Transaction	1.235	3	0.412	0.762	0.518
Quick Fund Transfer	0.592	3	0.197	0.431	0.731
Protecting Financial Information	4.761	3	1.587	2.744	0.046
Safety Ease of access	0.845	3	0.282	0.483	0.695

The data in Table 4 presents the ANOVA results for six distinct satisfaction aspects related to mobile banking: availability, control, safety of secure transactions, speedy fund transfer, protection of financial information, and safety and convenience of access. Additionally, it includes an overall satisfaction measure for mobile banking. There is no statistically significant variance in the overall satisfaction with mobile banking across users at the 0.05 level of significance. This is because the p-value (Sig.) is 0.117, which is more than 0.05. Thus, authors do not reject the null hypothesis. The p-values (Sig.) for the factors of availability, control, quick fund transfer, safety and ease of access, and minimizing human error are more than 0.05, showing that there are no significant differences in satisfaction levels across users for these factors. Regarding the protection of financial information, the p-value (Sig.) is 0.046, which is below the threshold of 0.05. This suggests a considerable disparity in satisfaction levels among users about this element. Consequently, authors refute the null hypothesis and embrace the alternative hypothesis, indicating a substantial disparity in satisfaction levels regarding the safeguarding of financial data among users.

Conclusion

Economic growth typically yields higher income levels and job opportunities, thus facilitating enhanced availability of financial services like banking, credit, and insurance. Enhanced accessibility can contribute to the alleviation of poverty and inequality, as well as the stimulation of economic growth. Furthermore, economic expansion can also result in the establishment of a

stronger and more varied financial industry. As the economy expands, there is a rise in the demand for financial services, which in turn leads to heightened rivalry among financial institutions. This competition has the potential to foster the development of novel financial services and products, thereby facilitating individuals and businesses in their access to financial services. As the proportion of the population who utilize the internet increases, so does the possibility for advancing financial inclusion through digital financial services. It facilitates individuals' inclusion in the official financial system and enhances their financial welfare. In addition, economic prosperity can facilitate the advancement of financial education and literacy, as individuals are inclined to actively pursue and comprehend financial products and services when they possess greater disposable income and financial stability. Financial inclusion and Fintech developments are essential catalysts for economic growth and development in any nation. The PMJDY is a prominent initiative for promoting financial inclusivity in India with the objective of providing universal access to financial services. The Indian government has led an ambitious project that has greatly enhanced the accessibility and affordability of financial services for marginalized groups. Additionally, this initiative has played a crucial role in fostering Fintech developments.

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